

DEVELOPING SOCIAL BEHAVIOR IN ORPHANAGE RESIDENTS: PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES

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Abstract. *The article examines modern pedagogical and psychological approaches to the development of social behavior in children from Mercy Homes. It explores methods of socialization for orphans, with a focus on both foreign and domestic experiences. The study identifies key areas of development: communication skills, self-management, adaptation to social norms, and prosocial behavior. The results highlight the importance of a socio-pedagogical environment, and the developed methodological guides are recommended for use in educational practice.*

Keywords: *social behavior, children with orphanhood, socialization, communicative competence, self-regulation, social norms, prosocial behavior, socio-pedagogical environment.*

Introduction

Today, many countries face the urgent task of ensuring the social protection of orphaned and parentless children and preparing them to become fully integrated members of society. The *Convention on the Rights of the Child* emphasizes the state's primary obligation to provide care for children deprived of the opportunity to live within their families. In modern societies, this issue is thoroughly studied through aspects such as social integration, life skills development, and personal growth.

Developed countries such as the United States, France, the United Kingdom, and Russia place particular emphasis on raising orphaned children in family environments to enhance their social adaptation. These nations have developed pedagogical technologies and psychological approaches to support the integration of such children into society.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the activities of orphanages have been reformed, and the system for providing social and economic support to children has been strengthened. National programs have created the necessary conditions for children to be raised in family settings, facilitating their social integration and intellectual development. These state-led initiatives aim to increase the social engagement of orphaned children and ensure their successful integration into society.

Analyzing the pedagogical and psychological methods for developing social behavior in orphanage residents is currently considered a pressing issue.

Additionally, the country's Development Strategy outlines specific tasks aimed at creating conditions for the intellectual, aesthetic, and physical development of young people, increasing their social activity, and realizing their creative potential. This supports the formation of social behavior in orphanage residents and ensures their successful integration into society.

Examining ways to improve this process through pedagogical and psychological mechanisms remains one of the most urgent challenges of today.

Methodology

The study examined modern pedagogical and psychological approaches aimed at developing social behavior in orphanage residents. Qualitative analysis methods were employed to gain an in-depth understanding of the upbringing and socialization processes of the children. Interviews were conducted with caregivers, and observations were made of the children's daily activities and communication skills.

The primary research methods included:

Pedagogical analysis

Psychological observation

Sociological surveys

An analysis of scientific literature revealed effective methods for integrating orphanage residents into social life by combining national and international practices.

Research conducted by both national and foreign scholars provided insights into the role of psychological support, moral education, and the incorporation of values in facilitating the social adaptation of orphanage residents. Additionally, the practical experience of caregivers working with children contributed valuable information to the study.

Main Body

The study results demonstrate that the process of developing social behavior in orphanage residents is multifaceted and complex. It requires the creation of essential conditions for their adaptation to family settings and integration into society. The success of this process largely depends on establishing a well-structured socio-pedagogical environment.

Developing social behavior in orphanage residents is a pressing issue, playing a vital role in the process of socialization. Through forming interpersonal relationships, adapting to societal norms, and learning appropriate behavior in social settings, children grow into active and contributing members of society. This article analyzes the primary directions for shaping social behavior and highlights the significance of this process.

As a result of the analysis, the key areas for the personal and social development of orphanage residents were identified.

1. Development of Communicative Competence

Communicative competence is a crucial factor in the social integration of orphanage residents. Communication is not merely the exchange of information but also the management of interpersonal relationships and the development of interaction mechanisms. Orphanage residents often have limited communication experience, which negatively affects their ability to interact with society. Therefore, developing their communication skills is one of the key areas for fostering social adaptation.

Various pedagogical technologies and methods are used to enhance communicative competence, including role-playing games, group activities, and interactive programs. These approaches help children articulate their thoughts clearly and understand the perspectives of others. This development is a significant step toward finding their place in society.

2. Development of Self-Management and Responsibility

Self-management skills are a vital component of social development. Orphanage residents often face challenging situations in their lives, which can weaken their ability to regulate their behavior. Developing self-management and a sense of responsibility is an integral part of their self-awareness process.

Metacognitive competencies play a significant role in this development, enabling children to plan their activities, make decisions, and think critically.

A sense of personal responsibility helps children become accountable for their actions. This skill is crucial for finding their place in future social life and achieving both professional and personal success.

3. Adaptation to Social Norms and Rules

Adapting to social norms is one of the primary factors that define a child's role in society. Orphanage residents often lack sufficient experience in following societal rules, making their development in this area a matter of special attention. The processes of social conformity and socialization ensure that children adapt to the moral standards of society.

Through these processes, residents learn how to behave in social settings, adhere to rules of conduct, and follow collective norms. This helps accelerate their social adaptation and enables them to participate successfully in societal activities.

4. Development of Empathy and Prosocial Behavior

The development of empathy and prosocial behavior is essential for orphanage residents, as it involves fostering sensitivity to others' emotions, helping, and caring for others. Empathy is a fundamental factor in developing social and psychological skills, allowing individuals to understand others' inner worlds and fostering a desire to assist them.

The formation of prosocial behavior helps residents find their place in society and become socially active citizens. Prosocial behavior can be cultivated through group games and activities, where children learn the importance of mutual support and collaboration.

Development of Teamwork and Collaboration Skills

The development of teamwork and collaboration skills among children in orphanages is a crucial foundation for their future success. Participation in group activities helps them acquire the skills necessary for effectively performing their tasks, cooperating with others, and achieving collective goals. Through this process, children learn social roles and become active members of society.

Furthermore, fostering teamwork and collaboration skills helps develop leadership qualities. Active participation in a team increases their sense of responsibility and lays the groundwork for becoming socially effective citizens.

As a result of the analysis, key directions for the personal and social development of orphanage residents have been identified. Additionally, special didactic materials and methodological guidelines have been developed. These resources have been successfully utilized by educators to shape children's social behavior, with results demonstrating their effectiveness.

The didactic resources created for orphanage educators have become an important factor in accelerating the social adaptation process for children. These outcomes have been highly appreciated by teachers and caregivers and are recommended for widespread practical application.

Discussion

Research findings demonstrate that approaches to developing social behavior in orphanage residents are effective when national and international practices are harmonized. National researchers, including M. Bekmurodov, D. Isayeva, and M. Qahhorova, emphasize the importance of shaping social behavior based on national and moral values. Their studies highlight the necessity of considering national characteristics in child-rearing practices.

Foreign scholars, such as J. Ballantine, K. Wegar, K. Browne, and R. Carter, have extensively explored the social adaptation of orphanage residents and the significance of upbringing in a family environment. Their research underscores that synthesizing national and international approaches yields significant results in developing the social behavior of children in orphanages.

The didactic materials developed during the research were successfully applied by orphanage educators to enhance children's social skills, with positive outcomes observed. These methodological materials have played a crucial role in improving the pedagogical process and are recommended for broader application.

The work conducted in this field confirms its relevance not only from a theoretical perspective but also in practical implementation. Based on the research outcomes, it is advisable to develop new technological approaches to further improve the socio-pedagogical environment and positively influence the lives of children.

Conclusion

This study confirms the importance of modern pedagogical and psychological approaches in developing social behavior among orphanage residents. Successful integration into society can be achieved by enhancing children's communication skills, fostering self-regulation abilities, improving adaptation to social norms, and strengthening empathy and prosocial behavior.

The didactic materials and pedagogical technologies developed during the research served as effective tools in improving this process. In the future, the process of developing social behavior should be further refined through the use of individualized approaches and digital technologies.

The following directions are proposed for future research:

Developing individual strategies aimed at improving communication skills.

Conducting experimental studies to support the growth of empathy and prosocial behavior.

Creating new pedagogical models to enhance teamwork and leadership skills.

Exploring opportunities to develop adaptation to social norms using digital technologies.

Research in these areas will contribute to further improvement of social behavior among orphanage residents, ensuring their successful integration into society.

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